

Some Thermodynamic Constants of [U(VI)]—[7-Chloro-8-Hydroxyquinoline-5-Sulphonic Acid] Chelate

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U(VI) forms in aqueous medium, a 1 : 2 complex with 7-chloro-8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid. The orange red complex has λ_{\max} at 355 m μ and is stable in the pH range 5.4 to 9.3. The stability constant and the free energy of formation of the complex are found to be $\log K = 9.43 \pm 0.35$ and $\Delta F = -13.07 \pm 0.49$ kcal/mole at 30°. The enthalpy change and entropy change calculated by temperature coefficient method and Gibbs-Helmholtz equation are found to be -8.70 kcal/mole and 12.85 e.u. respectively.

7-chloro-8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid, like its parent compound 8-quinolinol, acts as a very strong chelating agent. It forms water soluble complexes with a number of metal ions. Tiao-Hsu Chang and co-workers¹ have studied the stability constants of Ni, Co, Zn, Pb and Cd chelates with 7-chloro-8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid potentiometrically, but no significant work on the uranium chelate is on record. The present study deals with the investigation of [U(VI)]-[7-chloro-8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid] chelate spectrophotometrically regarding its composition, stability and thermodynamic parameters like ΔF , ΔH and ΔS , associated with the formation of the complex in aqueous medium.

Preparation of the reagent, metal solutions and the experimental details are similar to those described in our earlier publication².

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The effective pH range for the stable existence of the complex was found to be between 5.4 and 9.3. However pH 6.6 \pm 0.1 was selected for subsequent studies. Ammonium acetate buffer was used to maintain the constant pH.

The nature of the complex formed was studied by the method of Vosburgh and Cooper³ and it was found that only one complex is formed under the conditions of study, with λ_{\max} at 355 m μ .

The empirical formula of the complex in solution was established by three independent methods, the Continuous Variation method⁴, mole-ratio method⁵ and slope-ratio method⁶.

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The results indicate that one mole of uranium reacts with two moles of the reagent to form a stable complex in solution.

The stability constant of the complex has been calculated by the method of Banerji and Dey⁷, mole-ratio method and the method using molecular extinction coefficient data. The values obtained by these different methods are in close agreement and the mean value of $\log K = 9.43 \pm 0.35$ and the free energy of formation comes out to be $\Delta F = -13.07 \pm 0.49$ kcal/mole at 30° [$\Delta F = -RT \ln K$].

In view of the difficulty in obtaining thermodynamic stability constant (and hence ΔF), we have determined the stability constant and free energy of formation of the complex at a fixed ionic strength of 0.1, pH 6.6 ± 0.1 and at various temperatures. The results obtained have been presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1
Log K, ΔF and ΔS at various temperatures

Temp. °C	Log <i>k</i>	ΔF Kcals/mole	ΔS e.u.
20	9.293	-12.46	12.84
25	9.183	-12.52	12.83
30	9.079	-12.59	12.85
35	8.979	-12.66	12.86
40	8.882	-12.72	12.85
45	8.789	-12.78	12.84
	Average		12.85

From the slope of the curve, obtained by plotting $\log K$ against $1/T$, the enthalpy change [$\Delta H = 2.303 \cdot R \cdot (\log K_2 - \log K_1) \cdot 1/(1/T_1 - 1/T_2)$] of the reaction calculated by temperature coefficient method was found to be -8.696 kcal/mole. Assuming this to be constant over the range of temperatures employed, entropy change $\Delta S = \frac{\Delta H - \Delta F}{T}$ of the reaction has also been calculated, using Gibbs-Helmholtz equation and has been found to be 12.845 e.u.

The ability of 7-chloro-8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid to form metal chelates is due to the peri position of the phenolic hydroxyl group to the hetero atom nitrogen, forming a grouping N-C-C-O which can give rise to the formation of a five membered ring with a metal ion. During the chelation, the hydrogen atom of the hydroxyl group may be replaced by a number of metal ions^{8,9} and the coordination link may then be obtained between the

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metal atom and the adjacent nitrogen atom. A five-membered ring can thus be obtained in the structure of the complex molecule. The tentative structure of the chelate can be represented as follows :

A comparison of the stability constant and free energy of formation of [U(VI)]-[7-chloro-8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid] chelate ($\log K = 9.43 \pm 0.35$; $\Delta F = -13.07 \pm 0.49$ kcal/mole), with the corresponding [U(VI)]-[7-bromo-8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid] chelate (Corrected Values : $\log K = 9.76 \pm 0.45$; $\Delta F = (-13.54 \pm 0.62$ kcal/mole) reveals that the bromo derivative of 8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid forms more stable complexes than the corresponding chloro derivative. This is in accordance with the results obtained by Tiao-Hsu Chang and co-workers¹ and some of the results reported by us¹⁰⁻¹³. It may be due to the fact that the chloro derivative is more acidic than the bromo derivative.

The fact that the stability constant decreases with an increase in temperature and the low positive value of entropy of the complex clearly indicates that the reaction is exothermic.

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